

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MORPHOLOGICAL DETERMINANTS OF SPROUTING IN *ULMUS MINOR* MILL. AFTER FELLING: A CASE STUDY FROM AN URBAN GREEN SPACE IN SOFIA, BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

Resprouting is a critical persistence strategy for many broadleaved tree species after cutting or disturbance. This study investigates the relationships between morphological characteristics of felled *Ulmus minor* trees and the traits of their resprouts in an urban green area of Sofia, Bulgaria. Measurements were conducted on 111 stumps across three 100 m² plots, including stump diameter, tree age, and the number, height, and diameter of sprouts. Average values of sprout height and diameter were calculated from maximum and minimum measurements. The results revealed a strong positive correlation between stump diameter and tree age, as well as between stump size and sprout height. A negative relationship was found between the number of sprouts and their individual dimensions, indicating strong intraspecific competition. Larger stumps produced fewer but taller and more vigorous sprouts, while smaller stumps generated more numerous but thinner ones. These findings confirm general resprouting dynamics reported for other deciduous species and emphasize the ecological and management significance of resprouting capacity in *U. minor* under urban conditions.

Keywords: elm, resprouting; urban forestry; stump diameter; coppice regeneration; tree morphology; sanitary cutting; competition.

1. Introduction

Field elm (*Ulmus minor* Mill.) is a broadleaved tree widely distributed across Europe, particularly in lowland and hilly areas, river terraces, and floodplains. It prefers warm, fertile soils and is more drought-tolerant than other elm species such as *U. glabra* and *U. laevis* [1,2]. Due to its resilience to periodic drought and tolerance of anthropogenic influences, *U. minor* is often used in roadside plantings and urban greening initiatives [3]

However, the species is highly susceptible to Dutch elm disease (DED), caused by the fungi *Ophiostoma ulmi* and *O. novo-ulmi*, which has drastically reduced its populations during the 20th century (Brasier, 2000). Maintaining its regenerative potential through stump resprouting is therefore essential for the persistence and resilience of *U. minor* in urban landscapes [4].

Resprouting is a key survival strategy for many tree species subjected to sanitary cutting, disease, or mechanical damage. Morphological traits such as stump diameter, tree age, resource reserves in the root-stump system, and site conditions are decisive factors influencing the number, height, and diameter of sprouts [5,6].

The aim of the present study is to evaluate the relationships between the morphological characteristics of cut trees (*U. minor*) and the parameters of their sprouts (number, height, diameter), in order to assess the resprouting potential of this species under sanitary cutting and anthropogenic pressure in an urban environment.

2. Materials and methods

The study was conducted in 2022-2023 on a green area of about 1000 m² in the Student City district of southeastern Sofia (GPS coordinates 42°39'02.2" N 23°20'21.9"E). The area is spontaneously colonized by *Ulmus minor*. After tree removal, stumps with resprouts remained. The local climate is temperate-continental, with a mean annual temperature of 10 °C, average annual precipitation of 620 mm, and typical winter snow cover. The soils are classified as Technosols [7], with an Urban surface horizon (A_u), technogenic materials, and a disturbed profile due to construction.

Three adjacent sample plots of 100 m² were established. For each stump, measurements included: number of sprouts, stump diameter, tree age (from growth rings), maximum and minimum sprout height, and maximum and minimum sprout diameter. Average sprout height and diameter were calculated as the mean of maximum and minimum values.

In order to analyze the soil properties, five soil profiles were made in each of the sample plots. The soil samples were taken from the urban A_u horizon after morphological description of the soil profiles.

The following methods were used in the laboratory tests of the soil samples:

- content of soil organic matter (SOM, %) - according to the modified Turin method [8];
- total nitrogen content (total N, %) - a modified version of the classic Kjeldahl method (ISO 11261:2002);
- reaction of the soil solution (pH in extracted H₂O) – measured potentiometrically with a pH meter;
- C:N ratio – calculation method [9];

The results are processed by statistical programme STATISTICA 12. The arithmetical averages (Mean) and standard deviations (SD) have been calculated.

3. Results

In total, 111 stumps were measured across the three plots. The results are presented below with scatter plots showing the main relationships, as follows:

There is a strong positive correlation ($r \approx 0.82$), confirming that stump diameter is a reliable proxy for tree age (Fig. 1)

Fig 1. Relationship between stump diameter and tree age.

Larger and older stumps tend to produce taller sprouts, likely due to better-developed root systems and resource reserves (Fig. 2)

A negative correlation is observed ($r \approx -0.20$), indicating that stumps producing more sprouts develop thinner stems (Fig

Fig. 2. Relationship between stump diameter and average sprout height.

Fig. 3. Relationship between number of sprouts and average sprout diameter.

A weak negative trend shows that stumps with more sprouts tend to have shorter sprouts (Fig. 4)

Fig. 4. Relationship between number of sprouts and average sprout height.

A slight negative correlation suggests that larger stumps tend to produce fewer sprouts, concentrating resources in fewer but stronger shoots.

Fig. 5. Relationship between stump diameter and number of sprouts.

Tabl. 1.

Sample plot (SP)	Soil properties				
	Depth (cm) Au horizon M±SD	SOM % M±SD	Total N % M±SD	C:N	pH M±SD
1	51.8 ± 1.6	4.42 ± 0.02	0.281 ± 0.005	9.1	7.7 ± 0.002
2	40.6 ± 0.9	4.16 ± 0.03	0.195 ± 0.004	12.4	7.7 ± 0.002
3	41.6 ± 1.7	4.21 ± 0.02	0.202 ± 0.007	12.1	7.5 ± 0.004

Note: SOM – soil organic matter, M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation.

The results of the soil properties study are presented in Tabl. 1. The data indicate that the soil depth in the A_u horizon of the studied soils ranges from 40.6 to 51.8 cm, with soil organic matter content varying between 4.15 % and 4.42 %, total nitrogen content between 0.202 % and 0.281 %, pH from 7.5 to 7.7. The greatest depth of the surface A_u horizon and content of SOM and total N was found in the soil of SP-1. The C:N ratio values range from 9.1 to 12.4, with the lowest values in SP-1 (Tabl. 1). This indicates that the mineralization of soil organic matter is occurring most intensively.

4. Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that stump resprouting in *Ulmus minor* follows general patterns observed in other broadleaved species. Stump diameter was strongly related to tree age and positively correlated with sprout height, suggesting that larger stumps with well-developed root systems provide a stronger basis for regeneration. At the same time, a clear trade-off was observed between the number of sprouts and their individual growth, reflecting intraspecific competition for limited resources.

Similar dynamics have been reported for coppice regeneration in oaks (*Quercus*) and beeches (*Fagus*), where pre-disturbance tree size is a reliable predictor of sprouting vigor and long-term sprout performance [10, 11]. These findings support the broader ecological framework that identifies resprouting as a key persistence strategy for woody plants after disturbances such as cutting, fire, or browsing [5,6]

In urban environments, the ability of *U. minor* to regenerate through resprouting is of particular importance, as it helps compensate for losses caused by sanitary cutting, mechanical injuries, and stress from soil compaction or pollution. Although the species remains highly vulnerable to Dutch elm disease [12], its capacity to sprout from stumps provides opportunities for maintaining viable populations in urban ecosystems.

Soil conditions influence the regeneration of *Ulmus minor*. A greater stump diameter is observed in deeper and richer soils, with more intensive mineralization of organic matter.

From a management perspective, the results suggest that stump diameter should be considered as an indicator of regeneration potential when planning sanitary cuttings. Appropriate management of sprouts could improve the resilience of *U. minor* in urban habitats and help preserve its ecological and ornamental functions.

5. Conclusions

A clear trade-off between sprout number and individual growth (height and diameter) highlights strong intraspecific competition.

These patterns confirm the general ecological role of resprouting as a persistence strategy in broadleaved species and emphasize its importance for the resilience of *U. minor* in urban environments subject to disturbance.

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